

COMPUTER GAMES ARE A TOOL OF FUN.

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Abstract: Indulging in computer games has a lot of harm to society. First of all, it is a moral damage, computer games plunge our society into a morass of moral corruption and deprive a person of the happiness of self-awareness...

Key words: internet club, society, youth, people, child mentality.

As a specialist in the field of education, I often meet people who are surprised to see how quickly children of our time learn the functions of computer programs and mobile phones. Children who understand computer games at first glance and play them passionately surprise and worry adults. However, many children are given electronic toys as early as infancy. There are many such toys for children of different ages in toy stores. However, parents need to know how to choose them correctly.

Among the simplest computer games for children of preschool age, developmental, educational, arithmetic and language learning, drawing and various useful exercises, entertainment activities are presented in the form of games. Children like developing computer games. They are often created using cartoon characters in bright colors that are close to children. And those intended for school-aged children will be designed to provide students with science-related knowledge. The most popular computer games include: car, ship, plane and other racing games, as well as computer sports games. Such educational games can be obtained from the Zionet educational network.

Computer games are diverse, but it is not recommended to play all of them.

Classification of computer games

1. Strategic games.
2. Local games.
3. Sports games.
4. Logical games.
5. Imitation games.
6. Online games.

One of the games that are attracting interest among users are military strategy or war games. In these games, there are issues such as managing the entire army, carrying out construction work for defense, and planning fortification work there is. And the so-called Arcade and Quest games are focused on

achieving victory without using weapons by managing interesting processes, completing secret tasks and solving puzzles during the game.

Online games. In this game, not one, but several players control the game over the network. Such games develop communication skills in children. Of course, car racing is popular among boys, followed by sports such as football, hockey, boxing, basketball, chess, and golf. Because in these games it is possible to control one player or a group of players.

Puzzles or puzzles. It belongs to the category of simple games and is intended for younger users. There are many useful and developing games among them. Such games are recommended for learning the alphabet, arithmetic, drawing, and foreign languages with the participation of brightly colored cartoon characters. How useful are computer games? Many parents have probably noticed that since their children started playing computer games, they started using the expressions "I killed" or "They killed me" a lot. Currently, many young children are spending most of their time in those computer clubs. In order to continue the fun of yesterday, some of them even skip their classes at school.

Along with computer technologies, computer games are developing rapidly. We all know how realistic the virtual world is. The closer it is to reality, the more it attracts us. The creators of computer games pay great attention to it, its graphics, sound, etc. k. The closer the game is to reality, the higher its rating.

It's no secret that in most computer games, the main task (movement) is aimed at destruction or, if not, killing. How do you think a child who spends 2-3 hours in computer clubs, immersed in the intensity of events in the game, will be in the street? How long will it take him to return to real life after this game? I think that each of us has been in this situation many times.

For today's schoolchildren, it seems easier to press keyboard and mouse buttons for an hour than to read a book for an hour. Because there are many opportunities there. If you made a mistake, there is a chance to correct it again. If you die in Bordiu game, they will give you another chance to continue the game. In real life it is completely different. Undoubtedly, such games inevitably have a negative impact on the child's view of real life. It is also possible that he will not be able to give a correct assessment of his possibilities in real life.

In the healthy growth and development of a child, his interests, along with his food, friends, and education, are important. Currently, most children's passion is computer games, and it is often repeated that it is harmful.

Damages:

- inability to leave the game, computer or phone;

- spend money on paid games;
- humanization;
- lack of sleep;
- dry eyes, headache and back pain;
- increased fear, depression and anger.

Children between 10-18 years of age are very addicted to computer games. First of all, this is a waste of time. It all seems like it happened in a matter of minutes.

Just like there are two sides to a coin, these games have their pros and cons. First of all, it increases the level of assimilation of new knowledge.

Improves memory - learns to pay attention to the position of objects and people while playing the game. Since playing computer games with a keyboard and mouse, the fine motor skills of the hand develop well. Learning a field through the game - this is exactly what games are designed for. As we mentioned above, everything has its pros and cons. The main rule for a child is to know the norm and time limit. It is this habit that separates profit and loss.

Conclusion: computer games do more harm than good, as an example: they steal time, make a person nervous and stop thinking. we can join the ranks of developing countries. The most important thing is to avoid indifference so that we can achieve the results we expect.

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